

STUDY OF THE EFFECT OF FERTILIZING ON GRAIN PRODUCTIVITY

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Annotation: In the difficult climatic conditions of the Kostanay region, cultivated crops turned out to be responsive, first of all, to the application of nitrogen and phosphorus fertilizers. The success of the use of such tusks has been noted by many researchers, but the study of the effectiveness of sulfur-containing additives has not been carried out to an insufficient extent.

Key words: Kostanay region, nitrogen and phosphorus fertilizers, many researchers, but the study of the effectiveness, the development of a rational fertilizer application system

INTRODUCTION

Fertilization is the main factor in regulating plant nutrition and soil fertility by changing the content of available forms of necessary substances. Of undoubted interest in this area is the effectiveness of the use of various tusks in the cultivation of major crops, especially spring wheat.

Today, the development of a rational fertilizer application system is one of the priorities of agronomic science in many countries, including the Republic of Uzbekistan. This mechanism will make it possible to obtain high yields of crop-growing products that are competitive in quality, while simultaneously preserving and increasing soil fertility, as well as exerting an effective influence on grain quality. The experience of foreign colleagues is of great interest in this direction.

PROVIDE THE NEEDS

Today, the state policy of the Republic of Kazakhstan, as in our country, is aimed at guaranteeing the safety of food when consumed by the population. An important role in this area is given to increasing the collection of spring soft wheat grain — one of the main sources of nutrition. Under favorable conditions, the yield of this crop in the fields of experimental farms can reach 27-33 kg/ha, and with an increase in productivity to 15 kg/ha, the state can harvest up to 20-23 million tons of grain annually.

In the socio-economic development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the agro-industrial sector is given an important place, and its formation is of particular importance in the Kostanay region. The main commercial production of agricultural crops, including spring soft wheat, is concentrated in this region — 75-80% of all sown areas are used for it, and gross grain harvests average 8-12 million tons per year. It should be noted that the level of demand of farmers in the northern regions of this state for fertilizers is high. However, not all farms can provide themselves with them, so their acquisition is at a low level — no more than 25%, primarily due to high prices, lack of financial opportunities, especially for small and medium-sized agricultural firms, and weak state support. In this regard, the demand for additives and consumer activity are at a low level. Uzbekistan agricultural producers, of course, have a somewhat different situation, but for them, the formation of a rational system for the use of fertilizers is relevant in order to optimize and reduce costs.

METHOD AND RESULTS

In order to increase yields in the weather conditions of the sharply continental climate of the northern part of the Republic of Kazakhstan and to study the impact of fertilizing on grain productivity, specialists of Karabalyk Agricultural Experimental Station LLP conducted scientific research. Experiments were laid in the fields of this organization, their object was spring soft wheat of the Karabalyk 90 variety. On experimental plots of 5 hectares each, fertilizers were applied according to a certain scheme for the crop under consideration. The first option became a control, the second used ammophos with a content of 46-49% phosphorus oxide and 10-12% nitrogen. In the third section, ammonium sulfate with 20.5–21% nitrogen and 24% sulfur was used, in the fourth, ammonium nitrate was added in a dosage of 34.6% nitrogen. Ammonium sulfate and ammophos were introduced on the fifth plot, ammonium nitrate and ammophos were introduced on the sixth, sulfoammophos containing 20% nitrogen, 20% phosphorus and 14% sulfur was introduced on the seventh. The experience was laid down in threefold repetition, the placement of options was systematic. The total area of the experimental site was 105 hectares. Agrotechnics during the research consisted in the differentiated application of fertilizers on a hectare grid on average based on a dose of nitrogen of 60 kg of d. v. and 90 kg of d. v. phosphorus per hectare. Additives were introduced by a complex seeder in accordance with the scheme to a depth of 12-16 cm in the spring 10-15 days before sowing crops. This operation was carried out on May 26 with the help of a Horsh tractor and an Emmity brand complex to a depth of 6-8 cm.

RELIABLE INCREASE

In the difficult climatic conditions of the Kostanay region, cultivated crops turned out to be responsive, first of all, to the application of nitrogen and phosphorus fertilizers. The success of the use of such tuks has been noted by many researchers, but the study of the effectiveness of sulfur-containing additives has not been carried out to an insufficient extent. In the conditions of "Karabalyk Agricultural Experimental Station" LLP, the yield on the control variant without tuks was 12.1 c/ha. When applying fertilizers, this indicator increased from 13.6 to 17.5 c/ha, that is, by 1.5–5.4 c/ca, or 12.4–44.6%. Ammonium nitrate showed the greatest efficiency — the increase to the control reached 5.4 c/ha, that is, 44%, and this fertilizer together with ammophos — 5.1 c/h, or 42%. Thus, the difference in productivity confirmed that the use of tusks was effective for the culture under study, and in the conditions of the reporting year, a significant increase was provided by the use of sulfoammophos, ammonium nitrate both singly and in combination with ammophos.

One of the factors of intensification of agricultural production is the improvement of the quality of the products obtained. The analysis of the grain condition during the experiments confirmed that mineral fertilizers, along with an increase in the volume of collection, had a positive effect on the characteristics of raw materials, in particular the protein content. The gluten concentration also increased significantly with the introduction of nitrogen tuks, which acted as one of the ways to regulate the quality of the spring wheat crop. The highest content of this substance was observed at the site with ammonium nitrate and ammophos — 28.57%, while at the control this value was 23.42%. On the test version, the gluten index corresponded to class III grain, and when using ammonium sulfate or ammonium nitrate together with ammophos, it was possible to obtain products that meet Class I according to this criterion.

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